

CHANGING DYNAMICS OF TALIBAN-INDIA RELATIONS: IMPLICATIONS FOR PAKISTAN'S SECURITY AND STRATEGIC INTERESTS

Dr. Shahid Ali¹, Dr. Adnan Nawaz^{2*}

¹Assistant Professor, Department of International Relations, Lahore College for Women University (LCWU), Lahore.

²Assistant Professor, Department of International Relations, Government College University, Faisalabad.

¹shahidali436@gmail.com, ²adnannawaz@gcuf.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Adnan Nawaz

Abstract

This article explores the impact of growing Taliban-India ties on Pakistan's security and strategic interests. It argues that the Taliban's nascent rapprochement with India carries significant risks for Pakistan's national security and territorial integrity. Islamabad is concerned that the Taliban-India détente could allow New Delhi to trap Pakistan in the two-front situation, a scenario that Pakistan wants to avoid at all costs. Pakistan fears that India could use its improved relationship with the Taliban to support terrorist groups such as the Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan and the Baloch Liberation Army not only to destabilize subvert Pakistan's national security and territorial integrity but also sabotage the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Pakistan has intensified pressure on the Taliban to backtrack on its growing engagement with India and sever ties with the TTP and other terrorist groups. However, the Taliban have remained unwilling to cater to Pakistan's demands, causing serious rifts in Pakistan-Afghanistan relations.

Introduction

Since Pakistan's independence in 1947, the bilateral relationship between Islamabad and Kabul has been marked by tensions, hostility, and distrust. In the early period, Afghan government's reluctance to recognize the Durand Line border and its decision to support the creation of an independent Pashtunistan were the major reasons behind this acrimonious relationship. Following the British departure from India, Pakistan inherited the Durand Line border with Afghanistan. Nevertheless, Afghanistan's government repudiated Pakistani claims regarding the legality of the Durand Line, claiming that the treaties signed between the British Empire and Afghanistan became void upon the collapse of British Raj in India in 1947.¹ Furthermore, due to its reservations about the Durand Line's legal status and Pashtunistan issue, the Afghan government also opposed Pakistan's admission to the United Nations (UN), which generated serious rifts in the bilateral relations. Subsequently, the Durand Line dispute became a flashpoint between Islamabad and Kabul, with successive Afghan governments providing sanctuary, weapons, and material and diplomatic support

to the Pashtun and Baloch militants/separatists to exert pressure on Pakistan.²

In addition to the Durand Line dispute, Afghanistan's historically close relationship with India is another key irritant in Pakistan-Afghanistan ties. Despite Pakistan's concerns, Afghanistan has mostly enjoyed cordial relations with India starting from the "Treaty of Peace and Friendship" in January 1950. The only period Afghanistan had no cooperation with India was during the first Taliban rule from 1996 to 2001. During the Cold War, India supported Afghanistan's claims over the Durand Line and with the objective of keeping Pakistan enmeshed with Kabul on its western border. Moreover, Afghanistan's former President Mohammad Daoud Khan sought Indian support for his government's efforts to coerce Pakistan on the issue of Pashtunistan and the demarcation of the Durand Line. Following the ouster President Daoud's government, India recognized the pro-Soviet Afghan government and lent technical and humanitarian assistance/support to the Afghan government. India's growing involvement in Afghan affairs led Pakistan to see Afghanistan through the lens of strategic depth with an aim of installing a friendly and pro-Islamabad government in

¹ Ahmad Shayeq Qaseem, "Pak-Afghan Relations: The Durand Line Issue," *Policy Perspectives* 5, no. 2 (2008): 87-102.

² Khalid Humayun Nadiri, "Old Habits, New Consequences: Pakistan's Posture toward Afghanistan since 2001," *International Security* 39, no. 2 (2014): 132-168.

Kabul.³ As a result, Pakistan started establishing closer links with Islamist factions who rejected Afghanistan's claims on Pakistani territories and were opposed to any Indian influence in Afghanistan.⁴ During the Soviet occupation of Afghanistan, Pakistan's role as a frontline state in the US campaign to defeat the Soviet Union further enhanced Islamabad's influence in the country.

The end of Soviet occupation in 1989 marked the advent of civil war in Afghanistan. The civil war ended in 1992 after the establishment of a transitional government in Kabul. However, due to political fragmentation amongst the different Mujahideen factions, civil war again erupted in 1994, with the Taliban emerging as a formidable actor/force. In 1996, the Taliban captured power in Kabul and established the first "Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan (IEA)". The group controlled almost 90 percent of the country with the Ahmed Shah Masood-led Northern Alliance/National United Front backed by Russia, India and Iran resisting the Taliban's rule. The establishment of the Taliban government provided Pakistan with opportunity to fulfil its long-sought goal of establishing a friendly regime in Afghanistan and attaining strategic depth against India, which was forced to evacuate its embassy and recall its diplomatic

staff from Afghanistan. Given Pakistan's diplomatic recognition of the Taliban regime, India continued to cement closer linkages with the Northern Alliance. In early 2001, India reportedly supplied Northern Alliance forces with economic assistance, military equipment, and technical and defense advisors.

In October 2001, the Taliban regime collapsed after the US and NATO troops invaded Afghanistan due to the Taliban's unwillingness to hand over Osama bin Laden, the prime accused of the 9/11 attacks. In 2005, the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan (IRA) was established with Hamid Karzai as the first President. The formation of IRA government provided India with strategic space to consolidate its footprint in Afghanistan through economic aid and diplomatic and security assistance. India also provided military training to thousands of Afghan military personnel. India also provided more than US\$3 billion in official development assistance to Afghanistan, including agriculture, infrastructure, communication, dams, transport, energy generation projects in different regions of the country. This provided India with significant economic, political, and diplomatic and strategic influence in Afghanistan.

The withdrawal of US and NATO troops from Afghanistan in August 2021 resulted in the collapse of the Western-backed IRA government. Subsequently, the Taliban took over the country and reinstated the Islamic Emirate of

³ C. Christine Fair. *Fighting to the end: The Pakistan army's way of war*. Oxford University Press, 2014.

⁴ *Ibid.*

Afghanistan (IEA 2.0). The reinstatement of IEA 2.0 was seen by some experts/observers as a political and strategic victory for Pakistan. Pakistani politicians and leaders of religious parties congratulated the Taliban for their smashing victory over the US. Pakistan's former Prime Minister Imran Khan even commented that "Afghans had broken the shackles of slavery".⁵ Pakistan anticipated that the Taliban government would curtail India's political, economic, and strategic influence in Afghanistan, as the first round of the Taliban rule had done. Pakistan also hoped that the Taliban would expel the Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) from Afghanistan and resolve longstanding issues related to the Durand line and Pashtun nationalism.⁶

Islamabad had good reasons to believe that the Taliban regime would cater to Pakistan's critical security and strategic interests in Afghanistan. Pakistan was the first country to recognize the Taliban-led government in Kabul from 1996 to 2001. After the US invasion of Afghanistan ousted the Taliban in October 2001, the Taliban retreated to Pakistan's Pashtun-dominated tribal areas where Pakistani militant

groups provided the Taliban with sanctuary and support it required to wage insurgency against the US-led NATO forces and the former Afghan republic.⁷ Following President Trump's decision to start peace negotiations with the Taliban, Pakistan also facilitated the February 2020 US-Taliban peace deal in Doha, which eventually paved the way for the re-establishment of the IEA 2.0 in August 2021.⁸

After the formation of IEA 2.0, Pakistan concentrated on convincing the international community to develop a roadmap to recognize the Taliban government, arguing that incentives rather than sanctions would encourage the Taliban to adopt a moderate governance approach. In September 2021, Pakistan's former Prime Minister Imran Khan remarked in his address to the UN General Assembly that "if the international community incentivizes the Taliban to respect human rights, keep terrorists off their soil and have an inclusive government, it will be a win-win situation for everyone".⁹ Pakistan also initiated efforts to build regional consensus on the Taliban government's

⁵ Dawn, "PM Imran Talks About Overpowering 'Shackles of Slavery' at Single National Curriculum Launch," Dawn, August 16, 2021, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1640988>.

⁶ Muhammad Akram, Dania Mohamad, and Adeela Arshad-Ayaz, "How Was the Taliban 2.0 in Afghanistan Seen in Pakistan?," *Asian Journal of Comparative Politics* 9, no. 2 (2023): 274-90, <https://doi.org/10.1177/20578911231172197>.

⁷ Tricia Bacon, "A Fragile Equilibrium: Incentivizing Pakistan's Regional Recalibration," *The Washington Quarterly* 46, no. 2 (2023): 163-81, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163660x.2023.2225909>.

⁸ The Express Tribune, "Pakistan's Communication with Taliban Led to Doha Agreement," *The Express Tribune*, September 2, 2021, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2318279/pakistans-communication-with-taliban-led-to-doha-agreement>.

⁹ "At UN, Pakistan Prime Minister Urges 'Bold Steps' to Prevent Humanitarian Crisis Afghanistan," *UN News*, September 25, 2021, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2021/09/1101222>.

diplomatic recognition, setting up a regional forum for facilitating ministerial-level consultation among neighboring states—including Pakistan, Russia, Iran, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and China.¹⁰

Contrary to Islamabad's expectations, the revival of IEA 2.0 has marked a critical juncture in the Pakistan-Afghanistan bilateral relationship. In the past three and half years, Pakistan's relations with the Taliban regime have witnessed significant corrosion, with both Islamabad and Kabul indulging in public sparring and localized military skirmishes between Pakistani and the Taliban border forces, killing civilians and security personnel on both sides.¹¹ In addition, Pakistan has announced that it will no longer "advocate the Afghan Taliban's case at international level," and scale down its engagement with the Taliban government.¹² Pakistan has also expelled more than 541,000 undocumented Afghan refugees from Pakistan.¹³ Pakistan's recent policy and actions

toward Afghanistan is an indication that the situation between Pakistan and the Afghan Taliban is becoming increasingly tense, and the relationship between the once-strategic partners has hit major snags.

This article explores the impact of growing Taliban-India ties on Pakistan's security and strategic interests. It argues that the Taliban's nascent rapprochement with India carries significant risks for Pakistan's national security and territorial integrity. Islamabad is concerned that the Taliban-India détente could allow New Delhi to trap Pakistan in the two-front situation, a scenario that Pakistan wants to avoid at all costs. Pakistan fears that India could use its improved relationship with the Taliban to support terrorist groups such as the Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan and the Baloch Liberation Army not only to destabilize subvert Pakistan's national security and territorial integrity but also sabotage the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Pakistan has intensified pressure on the Taliban to backtrack on its growing engagement with India and sever ties with the TTP and other terrorist groups. However, the Taliban have remained unwilling to cater to Pakistan's demands, causing serious rifts in Pakistan-Afghanistan relations.

¹⁰ Naveed Siddiqui, "Making Efforts to Build 'Regional Consensus' on Afghanistan, Qureshi Tells Chinese FM," Dawn, August 18, 2021, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1641364>.

¹¹ Aditya Kumar Singh, "Pakistan's Taliban Conundrum," South Asian Voices, October 16, 2024, <https://southasianvoices.org/sec-m-in-n-pakistan-afghan-taliban-10-16-2024/>.

¹² Kamran Yousuf, "Pakistan Shifts Stance on Afghan Taliban," The Express Tribune, November 9, 2023, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2445604/pakistan-shifts-stance-on-afghan-taliban>.

¹³ Shalini Chawla, "Shrinking Carrots and Added Sticks: Will Pakistan's Afghan Strategy Fetch

Results?," Centre for Air Power Studies, November 29, 2023, <https://capsindia.org/shrinking-carrots-and-added-sticks-will-pakistans-afghan-strategy-fetch-results/# edn7>.

The article proceeds as follows. The first section examines the role of Pakistan's India-centric threat perception on its policies towards Afghanistan. It shows that how Pakistan's fears about a potential India-Afghanistan alliance to encircle/tarp Pakistan in two-front situation have shaped its foreign and security policy towards Afghanistan. Section two discusses the evolving dynamics of the Taliban-India relationship since the US withdrawal from Afghanistan. It highlights the role of shifting geopolitical and economic interests in shaping the India-Taliban rapprochement. It explains that despite having a long history of troubled relations, both India and the Taliban are undertaking a paradigm shift in their relations, with both countries expressing willingness to enhance cooperation in trade and economic ties, industrial and infrastructure development, and even in military training. Section three examines the impact of the Taliban-India détente on the relationship between Pakistan and IEA 2.0. It demonstrates that the Taliban's burgeoning relationship with India undermines Pakistan's longstanding quest for strategic depth in Afghanistan. It shows that Pakistan is apprehensive that India could use its growing engagement with the Taliban to destabilize Pakistan and subvert its national security and territorial integrity by sponsoring terrorist group such as the TTP and BLA. It also shows that India could also use the TTP and BLA to

sabotage the development of CPEC and to destabilize Pakistan's relationship with China. The conclusion summarizes the argument.

Pakistan's India-centric Threat Perceptions and Policy toward Afghanistan

The partition of India in 1947 and the subsequent emergence of Pakistan as an independent state gave birth to an enduring rivalry/conflict between Pakistan and India (with unsettled territorial dispute over Kashmir being the central element of this rivalry) that has shaped almost every dimension of Pakistan's foreign and security policy, including its policy towards Afghanistan.¹⁴ Faced with a persistent threat and insecurity at the eastern border with India, Pakistan is loath to allow any hostile actor to also gain influence or undertake a predominant role/position in Afghanistan.¹⁵ This geostrategic predicament has generated concerns within Pakistan's foreign policy circles that an unfriendly Afghan government/regime could develop an alliance with India to trap Pakistan in a two-front scenario, which potentially undermine Pakistan's territorial integrity and national sovereignty. Thus, blocking/contesting India's geostrategic influence and preventing the emergence/rise of a New Delhi-aligned regime in Kabul has been

¹⁴ John Mitton, "The India-Pakistan Rivalry and Failure in Afghanistan," *International Journal* 69, no. 3 (2014): 353-76, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020702014540281>.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

one of the central elements of Pakistan's foreign policy toward Afghanistan.¹⁶

However, the Taliban's nascent rapprochement with India threatens Pakistan's strategic and security interests. Historically, Pakistan has seen India's presence and involvement in Afghanistan as a zero-sum game in which any gains for India are interpreted as losses for Pakistan.¹⁷ According to this logic, whatever India does in Afghanistan is considered as a tactic/move against Pakistan and its interests, whether it is economic assistance, infrastructure development, diplomatic engagement, or any other related matter.¹⁸ At the core of Islamabad's strategic considerations is a deep-rooted concern that if India could establish a base in Afghanistan, it would enable New Delhi to operate independently or collaborate with a sympathetic Afghan regime in Kabul to jeopardize Pakistan's national security and territorial integrity, especially by inciting unrest

in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan.¹⁹ This concern about India's presence in Afghanistan may lead Islamabad to "believe that New Delhi is trying to shield the Taliban from Pakistani pressure, particularly regarding the Taliban's support for the TTP—a group that Pakistan has long insisted is backed by India".²⁰

Pakistan's India-centric threat perception has its roots in the belief that India has never quite come to terms with the 1947 partition of the subcontinent and has been eager to undo Pakistan's existence as an independent state.²¹ Particularly, India's military intervention in East Pakistan and the subsequent emergence of an independent Bangladesh in 1971 catalyzed an insecurity syndrome in the minds of Pakistani leadership that India, which always has enjoyed closer ties with Kabul, could use its greater influence in Afghanistan to pose a backdoor military threat to Pakistan or even dismember the Pakistani state.²² More specifically, there

¹⁶ Ashley J. Tellis and Aroop Mukharji, "Is a regional strategy viable in Afghanistan." Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Washington DC: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. Online verfügbar unter http://carnegieendowment.org/files/regional_approach.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 25 (2010): 2015.

¹⁷ Hanifur Rehman and Faheem Ullah Khan Khan, "Indo-Pakistan Zero-Sum Rivalry and Afghanistan," *Journal of Contemporary Studies* 3, no. 2 (2014): 15-27.

¹⁸ Tricia Bacon and Asfandyar Mir, "India's Gamble in Afghanistan: The Promise and Peril of Rapprochement with the Taliban," *Foreign Affairs*, April 19, 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/afghanistan/2022-07-11/indias-gamble-afghanistan>.

¹⁹ C. Christine Fair. *Fighting to the end: The Pakistan army's way of war*. Oxford University Press, 2014.

²⁰ Tricia Bacon and Asfandyar Mir, "India's Gamble in Afghanistan: The Promise and Peril of Rapprochement with the Taliban," *Foreign Affairs*, April 19, 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/afghanistan/2022-07-11/indias-gamble-afghanistan>.

²¹ Sarita S. Dwivedi, "India as a dominant security concern to Pakistan (1947-1980)," *The Indian Journal of Political Science* 69, no. 3 (2008): 353-376.

²² John Mitton, "The India-Pakistan Rivalry and Failure in Afghanistan," *International Journal* 69, no. 3 (2014): 353-76, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020702014540281>.

existed a deeply entrenched belief among Pakistani policymakers that a potential convergence of interests between India and Afghanistan was very much possible as both countries have territorial and border disputes with Pakistan: Afghanistan over the Durand Line and India over Kashmir.²³

This perceived threat led Pakistan to place Afghanistan at the forefront of its security considerations, leading Islamabad to pursue the policy of cultivating a pliable/friendly Taliban regime in Kabul, believing that the Taliban was its best option to remove India's influence from Afghanistan.²⁴ Initially, Pakistan's strategic depth policy came to fruition during the Taliban's first turn in power as the IEA 1.0 pushed India out of Afghanistan and kept the Northern Alliance out of power. The establishment of a pro-Islamabad regime in Kabul also provided Pakistan with a sense of security regarding its western border as the Taliban government adopted a passive policy on the issue of Pashtunistan.

However, the Taliban's ouster from power in 2001 dealt a huge blow to Pakistan's interests in Afghanistan. President Hamid Karzai-led

Afghan government adopted an unfriendly approach toward Pakistan. On the other hand, India found close allies in the Pakistan-averse Northern Alliance coalition, which took key posts in the new Afghan government. It was the first time since the Soviet withdrawal that Pakistan was left out of the loop in Afghanistan. During the 20 years of the Afghan republic, India's involvement/engagement in Afghanistan was predicated on three key goals/objectives: first, to prevent the return of the Taliban and any other anti-India actor in Afghanistan; second, limit Pakistan's influence over any future regime in Afghanistan; third, to foster long-term economic and diplomatic ties with a pro-India regime in Afghanistan to counter Pakistan and establish trade and economic relations with energy-rich Central Asian Republics.²⁵

These objectives directly clashed with Pakistan's security and strategic interests in Afghanistan. Pakistan views a strong Indian presence in Afghanistan as tantamount to strategic encirclement, where it sees itself to be surrounded by inimical forces, with China being the only friendly neighbor. Therefore, when India reinstated its embassy in Kabul and opened consulates in Kandahar, Jalalabad, Herat, and Mazar-i-Sharif, Islamabad interpreted

²³ Zahoor Ahmad Wani, "Geopolitical Dynamics in the Afghanistan-India-Pakistan Triangle," *India Quarterly a Journal of International Affairs* 78, no. 4 (2022): 617-33, <https://doi.org/10.1177/09749284221127807>.

²⁴ Tricia Bacon, "A Fragile Equilibrium: Incentivizing Pakistan's Regional Recalibration," *The Washington Quarterly* 46, no. 2 (2023): 163-81, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163660x.2023.2225909>.

²⁵ Syed Kamal Shah and Safdar Hussain, "Drivers of Pakistan's Afghanistan Policy," *Pakistan Horizon* 75, no. 1 (2022): 67-85.

these moves as an attempt to undermine Pakistan's domestic security and weaken its ties with Kabul.²⁶ Subsequently, Islamabad repeatedly accused India of using Afghan soil to provide arms and financial assistance to the TTP and Baloch separatist groups to fuel unrest in Pakistan.²⁷

The relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan took a downturn after President Hamid Karzai accused Pakistan of harboring the Taliban leadership and termed the Durand Line as a "line of hatred as it raised a wall between two brothers". The Hamid Karzai government also revived the Pashtunistan issue by officially declaring August 31 as the "Pashtunistan Day" in Afghanistan. The Afghan government's friendly approach towards India and New Delhi's leading role in the reconstruction of Afghanistan perturbed the Pakistani policymakers, who viewed India's ascendance in Afghan affairs as a strategic loss and a major blow to Pakistan's decades-long efforts to establish an Islamist alliance between Kabul and Islamabad. For Pakistan, "a way out of this predicament was to return to the golden age of the late-1990s, when it had attained strategic depth in Afghanistan by keeping India out, the

Taliban in, and the Northern Alliance down".²⁸ Thus, when the Taliban retook power in Afghanistan in August 2021, Islamabad expected that the Taliban's foreign policy would look after Pakistan's core geostrategic and geo-economic interests, especially Pakistan's core interests vis-à-vis India.²⁹

However, Islamabad's expectations of cooperation with the Taliban to check or limit India's activities and influence in Afghanistan have been belied. Contrary to Pakistan's expectations, the Taliban have not only allowed India to re-establish its embassy in Kabul but also manifested a strong desire for developing closer ties with and even a readiness to accept military training from India. This is hardly surprising. The Taliban are aware that India is a rising economic power and an important player in regional and global geopolitical affairs. And given that New Delhi can deliver the much-needed financing for Afghanistan's reconstruction and development, the Taliban see no incentives in keeping India at bay. Cultivating closer relations with India could also help the Taliban ease its diplomatic isolation as New Delhi may use its rapidly growing

²⁶ Zahid Shahab Ahmed and Stuti Bhatnagar. "Pakistan-Afghanistan Relations and the Indian Factor," *Pakistan Horizon* 60, no. 2 (2007): 159-74.

²⁷ Baqir Sajjad Syed, "Specific Proof of Indian Terrorism in Pakistan Unveiled," *Dawn*, November 15, 2020, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1590441>.

²⁸ Peter R Mansoor, "The United States and Pakistan: Frenemies on the Brink," Hoover Institution, April 26, 2018, <https://www.hoover.org/research/united-states-and-pakistan-frenemies-brink>.

²⁹ Siegfried O. Wolf, "Pakistan's Failure in Afghanistan" January 10, 2023, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4322346>.

geopolitical leverage to lean on other countries such as Iran, Russia, and even the US to work with the Taliban.

The Taliban also hope that a détente with India would dissuade New Delhi from supporting the non-Taliban Afghan leaders, “especially because India is one of the few external actors positioned to energize political opposition in Afghanistan”.³⁰ The Taliban wants to prevent the collapse of the IEA 2.0 and has been exploring alternatives to end their diplomatic isolation and avoid over-dependence on Pakistan. The Taliban are aware that Pakistan by itself lacks the resources to guarantee the survival of IEA 2.0. The Taliban believe that a rising India may use its political and diplomatic clout to enhance the IEA 2.0’s ties with regional countries. At the same time, a robust relationship with the Taliban could provide India with strategic depth into Afghanistan, portending a remarkable reversal of fortunes for Pakistan, given its decades-long efforts to establish an Islamist alliance between Islamabad and Kabul to attain strategic depth and political influence in Afghanistan.

Taliban’s Rapprochement with India since the US withdrawal from Afghanistan

Since the revival of IEA 2.0, the Taliban’s changing/improving relationship with India has become another major irritant in Pakistan-Afghanistan ties. Recently, the Taliban have signaled that they are willing to foster meaningful relations with India, including establishing defense/security ties. In June 2022, the Taliban’s Acting Defense Minister, Mullah Yaqoob indicated that IEA 2.0 was ready “to send Afghan army personnel to India for military training stating that the Taliban don’t have any issues with it”.³¹ Speaking on the issue of Pakistan’s concerns over the Taliban’s warming ties with India, Mullah Yaqoob remarked: “We are an independent country, and our foreign policy is guided by our national interests”.³² Likewise, the Taliban interior minister Sirajuddin Haqqani stated in August 2022 that Afghanistan needs India’s cooperation to secure a peaceful environment in the country and to initiate reconstruction and development projects, urging Indian firms to resume work on stalled infrastructure projects.³³

³⁰ Tricia Bacon and Asfandyar Mir, “India’s Gamble in Afghanistan: The Promise and Peril of Rapprochement with the Taliban,” *Foreign Affairs*, April 19, 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/afghanistan/2022-07-11/indias-gamble-afghanistan>.

³¹ The Express Tribune, “Taliban Willing to Send Afghan Troops to India for Training: Mullah Yaqoob,” *The Express Tribune*, June 4, 2022, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2360038/no-issues-in-sending-army-personnel-to-india-for-training-taliban>.

³² Ibid.

³³ Shilpy Bisht and Manoj Gupta, “Exclusive | Afghanistan Needs India’s Help ‘Desperately’ to Secure Peaceful Environment: Taliban Interior M,”

On the other hand, India, which was forced to evacuate its embassy and pullout its diplomatic staff from Kabul after the fall of IRA government, has reciprocated with considerable dispatch to improve its relations with the Taliban and to secure a substantial footprint/presence in Afghanistan. In June 2022, India reopened its embassy in Kabul and deployed a technical mission to re-establish its diplomatic presence in Afghanistan. India has also delivered a sizable amount of wheat and medical supplies as a part of its humanitarian aid program, including 50,000 metric tons (MT) of wheat, 300 tons of medical assistance, including 1.5 million doses of COVID-19 vaccines, 27 tons on earthquake relief aid, 40,000 liters of pesticides, 100 million polio doses, and 11,000 units of hygiene kits for the drug de-addiction program.³⁴ Moreover, the Indian government has allocated a US\$25 million development aid package for Afghanistan in its 2023-24 budget.³⁵ In addition,

News18, August 2, 2022, <https://www.news18.com/news/world/exclusive-afghanistan-needs-indias-help-desperately-to-secure-peaceful-environment-taliban-interior-minister-haqqani-5670295.html>.

³⁴ "Foreign Secretary's Meeting with the Acting Foreign Minister of Afghanistan," Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, January 8, 2025, https://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/38898/Foreign_Secretarys_meeting_with_the_Acting_Foreign_Minister_of_Afghanistan.

³⁵ Fidel Rahmati, "India Announces Rs. 200 Crore Development Aid for Afghanistan in Budget 2023-24," Khaama Press, February 3, 2023,

India's foreign ministry also sent a special invitation to the Taliban officials to attend a four-day virtual course on Indian culture, legislation, and business environment, demonstrating that the ties between India and the Taliban are improving both in terms of rhetoric and actions.

In January 2025, Indian Foreign Secretary Vikram Misri met with Afghanistan's acting Foreign Minister Amir Khan Muttaqi in Dubai.³⁶ The meeting was the highest-level interaction between India and the Taliban government since the revival of IEA 2.0 in August 2021. In the meeting, Indian Foreign Secretary not only reaffirmed New Delhi's commitment to extend humanitarian assistance to Afghanistan but also emphasized the importance of enhancing/strengthening India-Afghanistan bilateral relations. Both countries agreed to promote the use of Chabahar port to enhance bilateral trade and commercial activities.³⁷ Notably, Afghanistan's Foreign Minister called India as a "significant regional and economic partner, acknowledged India's security concerns, and agreed to continue

<https://www.khaama.com/india-announces-rs-200-crore-development-aid-for-afghanistan-in-budget-2023-24/>.

³⁶ "Foreign Secretary's Meeting with the Acting Foreign Minister of Afghanistan," Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, January 8, 2025, https://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/38898/Foreign_Secretarys_meeting_with_the_Acting_Foreign_Minister_of_Afghanistan.

³⁷ Ibid.

regular contact at various levels”.³⁸ This statement indicates that after two decades of hostile relations, both Kabul and New Delhi are now moving toward a pragmatic reset in their bilateral relationship.

In the past, India had pursued an anti-Taliban policy in Afghanistan, believing that the group was a proxy of Pakistan.³⁹ During IEA 1.0, New Delhi provided logistical support and military equipment to the Northern Alliance forces. After the Taliban’s removal from power in 2001, India established robust economic, political, and security ties with the successive Afghan governments led by presidents Hamid Karzai and Ashraf Ghani. To reaffirm its commitment toward the democratic government in Afghanistan, New Delhi signed a Strategic Partnership Agreement with Kabul in 2011.⁴⁰ Under the agreement, India provided military training to Afghan security forces and invested in social and economic development with people-to-people contact, trade deals, cultural associations, and military visit exchanges.⁴¹

³⁸ Al Jazeera, “Taliban Calls India a ‘Significant Regional Partner’ After Officials Meet,” Al Jazeera, January 9, 2025, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2025/1/9/taliban-calls-india-a-significant-regional-partner-after-officials-meet>.

³⁹ Sumit Ganguly and Nicholas Howenstein, “India-Pakistan Rivalry in Afghanistan,” *Journal of International Affairs* 63, no. 1 (2009): 127–40.

⁴⁰ Muhammad Farooq, “India Engagement with Taliban-led Afghanistan and Implications for Pakistan,” *Margalla Papers* 26, no. 2 (2022): 87–95, <https://doi.org/10.54690/margallapapers.26.2.116>.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

Between 2004 and 2021, India also augmented the defense capabilities of the Afghan security forces by providing military training to its cadets, extending technical support to Afghan Air Force to maintain its fleet of MiG21 fighter jets, and delivering other defense-related equipment such as Mi-25 gunship helicopters.⁴² More importantly, India persistently criticized direct talks/negotiations between the US and the Taliban and consistently advocated for “an Afghan-led, Afghan-owned and Afghan-controlled peace and reconciliation process,” arguing that any unilateral agreement with the Taliban would undermine the fledgling democratic system in Afghanistan.⁴³

Given India’s previous unfriendly relations and policies toward the Taliban regime as well as the Taliban’s own hostile attitudes towards India, the IEA 2.0’s decision to engage with India and allow the reopening of the Indian embassy in Kabul signifies a critical shift in its decades-old policy toward New Delhi. For the past twenty years, the Taliban lamented India’s unwavering determination to support the Afghan republic

⁴² Rudra Chaudhuri and Shreyas Shende, “Dealing with the Taliban: India’s Strategy in Afghanistan After U.S. Withdrawal,” *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, June 2, 2020, <https://carnegieindia.org/2020/06/02/dealing-with-taliban-india-s-strategy-in-afghanistan-after-u.s.-withdrawal-pub-81951>.

⁴³ Elizabeth Roche, “India Committed to Unified, Democratic and Peaceful Afghanistan,” *Mint*, February 29, 2020, <https://www.livemint.com/news/world/india-committed-to-unified-democratic-and-peaceful-afghanistan-11582949699491.html>.

and repeatedly targeted the Indian embassy in Kabul and consulates in other cities of Afghanistan, including the July 2008 and October 2009 attacks on the Indian embassy in Kabul.⁴⁴ Moreover, throughout their previous stint in power between 1996 and 2001, the Taliban maintained an antagonistic approach toward India and provided support and sanctuary to anti-India militant groups such as Jaish-e-Mohammed (JeM), Lashkar-e-Taiba (LeT), Harkat-ul-Mujahideen (HuM) and Al-Qaeda in the Indian Subcontinent (AQIS).⁴⁵

Most notably, it was the Taliban regime that allowed the HuM militants to bring the hijacked Indian Airlines Flight 814 to Kandahar airport in 1999 and eventually helped them secure the release of fellow Islamist militants from Indian prisons, including the JeM chief Maulana Masood Azhar, Ahmed Omar Saeed Sheikh (indicted in the kidnapping and murder of American journalist Daniel Perl), and Kashmiri militant leader Mushtaq Ahmed

Zargar.⁴⁶ Given this perilous history, the statement from the Taliban Defense Minister Mullah Yaqoob that the Taliban would not permit anyone to use Afghan territory to launch attacks against India and that the IEA 2.0 would be interested in sending Taliban cadres to India for military training indicates that the Taliban are undertaking a pragmatic shift in its policy toward India.⁴⁷ Likewise, the Taliban's assurances about counter-terrorist operations against anti-India militant groups like JeM and LeT and their enthusiasm toward India's developmental projects, especially the Chabahar port, suggest that the Taliban have modified their approach toward their bilateral relations with India.

The Implications of India-Taliban Détente for Pakistan's Strategic Interests

The Taliban's détente with India carries significant risks for Pakistan's internal and external security. Islamabad is worried that the Taliban's closer relationship with India would allow New Delhi to subvert domestic peace, security, and stability in Pakistan's Balochistan

⁴⁴ Tricia Bacon and Asfandyar Mir, "India's Gamble in Afghanistan: The Promise and Peril of Rapprochement with the Taliban," *Foreign Affairs*, April 19, 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/afghanistan/2022-07-11/indias-gamble-afghanistan>.

⁴⁵ Shahid Ali, "The Specter of Hate and Intolerance: Sectarian-jihadi Nexus and the Persecution of Hazara Shia Community in Pakistan," *Contemporary South Asia* 29, no. 2 (2020): 198–211, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09584935.2020.1855114>.

⁴⁶ Rohan Gunaratna, *Inside Al Qaeda: Global Network of Terror*. Columbia University Press, 2002.

⁴⁷ Tricia Bacon and Asfandyar Mir, "India's Gamble in Afghanistan: The Promise and Peril of Rapprochement with the Taliban," *Foreign Affairs*, April 19, 2023, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/afghanistan/2022-07-11/indias-gamble-afghanistan>.

and KP provinces.⁴⁸ As discussed above, the Pakistani government has repeatedly accused India of fomenting terrorism in the country, funneling money and providing arms and training to the TTP and Baloch separatist groups such as BLA.⁴⁹ Notably, Pakistan has also accused the former Afghan government led by President Ashraf Ghani of collaborating with India to support the TTP and anti-Pakistan terrorist groups to subvert Pakistan's territorial integrity and national sovereignty.⁵⁰ In 2016, Pakistan arrested Kulbhushan Jadhav, a serving officer in India's intelligence agency "research analysis wing (RAW)" in Balochistan.⁵¹ Jadhav was allegedly collaborating with Baloch insurgent groups to undertake attacks against Pakistani security forces, LEAs, and Chinese nationals to sabotage the development of the CPEC.⁵² In 2020, Pakistan's then-Foreign Minister Shah Mehmood Qureshi accused India of running dozens of terrorist training camps in Afghanistan to foment terrorism in Pakistan, claiming that the Pakistani government had

irrefutable evidence of India's involvement in a wave of terrorist attacks in the country.⁵³

Pakistan's policymaking circles believe that India could use its closer ties with the Taliban to sabotage the CPEC and China-Pakistan relations. Due to the Taliban's linkages with the China-hostile groups, particularly with the TTP, the BLA, and East Turkistan Islamic Movement (ETIM), India could use TTP and BLA to jeopardize the CPEC through increased terrorism against Chinese projects and personnel in Pakistan.⁵⁴ It may also dent Pakistan's ambitions to potentially link up the CPEC with the "China-Central Asia-West Asia Economic Corridor through Afghanistan".⁵⁵ It may also negatively affect Pakistan-China bilateral relations and lead to an exit of Chinese capital from the country, which will put extra burden on Pakistan's already declining economy. Historically, India has opposed the CPEC on the grounds that it impinges on India's

⁴⁸ Mirwais Balkhi, "BJP-Taliban Ties and Their Implications," Wilson Center, March 5, 2001, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/blog-post/bjp-taliban-ties-and-their-implications>.

⁴⁹ Naveed Siddiqui, "Irrefutable Evidence Dossier on India's Sponsorship of State Terrorism in Pakistan Presented," Dawn, November 15, 2020, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1590333>.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Dawn, "Govt Airs Video of Indian Spy Admitting Involvement in Balochistan Insurgency," Dawn, July 17, 2019, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1248669>.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Ayaz Gul, "Pakistan Claims 'Irrefutable Evidence' of Indian Links to Terrorism on Pakistani Soil," Voice of America, November 14, 2020, https://www.voanews.com/a/south-central-asia_pakistan-claims-irrefutable-evidence-indian-links-terrorism-pakistani-soil/6198372.html.

⁵⁴ Syed Fazal-e-Haider, "Pakistan: The Dangerous Reality of Working on China's Megaprojects," *Lowy Institute*, April 5, 2024, <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/pakistan-dangerous-reality-working-china-s-megaprojects>.

⁵⁵ PIPS, "The Emerging Role of India in Afghanistan: Pakistan's Concerns and Policy Response," Pak Institute for Peace Studies (PIPS) (blog), May 2, 2023, <https://www.pakpips.com/article/7602>.

sovereignty because it passes through the Gilgit-Baltistan region, which New Delhi sees as a part of its territory.⁵⁶ Moreover, India sees the extensions of the CPEC into Afghanistan as a potent challenge to its geo-economic and geostrategic goals in Central Asia and beyond.⁵⁷ Particularly, India is concerned that the CPEC's extension into Afghanistan would undermine its investment in Iran's Chahbahar port and undercut India's ambitions to become a key economic, political, and strategic partner of the Taliban-led Afghanistan in the post-US withdrawal era.⁵⁸ For all these reasons, Pakistan is worried that India could use its improved relationship with the Taliban to form a nexus with the TTP and Baloch separatist groups to jeopardize the CPEC and Pakistan's geo-economic and geostrategic ties with China. Pakistan repeatedly claimed that during the tenure of the former Afghan republic from 2005-2021, India was using Afghan soil to sabotage the CPEC projects through the TTP, which perpetrates attacks on Pakistan from its sanctuaries in Afghanistan, as well as Baloch

⁵⁶ Muhammad Sohail Mushtaq and Muhammad Riaz Shad, "Belt and road initiative in South Asia," *Strategic Studies* 42, no. 2 (2022): 72-86.

⁵⁷ Shivam Shekhawat, "Betting on Connectivity: Afghanistan's China-Pakistan Economic Corridor Ambitions," *orfonline.org*, December 4, 2023, <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/betting-on-connectivity/>.

⁵⁸ Manish and Prashant Kaushik, "CPEC, Afghanistan and India's Concerns," *India Quarterly* A Journal of International Affairs 75, no. 2 (2019): 253-61, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974928419841790>.

separatist groups that Islamabad believes benefit from India's support.⁵⁹

Since the Taliban's return to power, the TTP has undertaken several high-profile attacks against the Chinese nationals working on the CPEC projects in different parts of Pakistan. In March 2024, the TTP's targeted suicide attack killed five Chinese engineers working on Dasu Dam project in the KPK province.⁶⁰ Later on, investigations revealed that the attacker was an Afghan national, and the vehicle used in the attack was smuggled into Pakistan through Chaman border checkpoint at the Durand Line border.⁶¹ Earlier in July 2021, the TTP killed nine Chinese workers in a suicide attack in Dasu, KPK.⁶² In April 2021, the group carried out a suicide attack on Quetta's Sarena hotel

⁵⁹ Muhammad Wasama Khalid, "India's Strategic Use of TTP to Undermine Pakistan's Stability," *Modern Diplomacy*, February 2, 2023, <https://moderndiplomacy.eu/2023/02/02/indias-strategic-use-of-ttp-to-undermine-pakistans-stability/>.

⁶⁰ Umar Bacha and Baqir Sajjad Syed, "China seeks answers after engineers killed in Bisham," *Dawn*, March 27, 2024, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1824034>.

⁶¹ Kamran Yousaf, "Probe points to Afghan link in suicide attack on Chinese engineers," *The Express Tribune*, April 2, 2024, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2461401/probe-points-to-afghan-link-in-suicide-attack-on-chinese-engineers>

⁶² RFE/RL's Radio Mashaal, "China, Pakistan Disagree Over Cause of Bus Explosion That Killed Several Chinese Workers," *Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty*, July 14, 2021, <https://www.rferl.org/a/pakistan-blast-chinese-workers-bri/31357651.html>.

where Chinese ambassador Nong Rong was staying.⁶³

Pakistan has repeatedly claimed that the Taliban are aiding the TTP with sanctuary and support in Afghanistan, allowing the group unimpeded operational freedom and mobility and access to advanced combat weapons left behind the US and NATO forces.⁶⁴ In February 2025, “the United Nations Security Council’s (UNSC) Analytical Support and Sanctions Monitoring Team” reported that the Taliban have been providing the TTP with logistical, operational, and financial support while enhancing recruitment within TTP cadres, including Afghan Taliban fighters.⁶⁵ The report also highlighted increased collaboration between the TTP, the Taliban, and Al-Qaeda in the Indian Subcontinent (AQIS). Consequently, the threat faced by Pakistan from the TTP has increased substantially with the group increasing its attacks against Pakistan’s security forces and LEAs. According to the Pakistan Institute for Peace Studies (PIPS), terrorist attacks in Pakistan significantly increased from 306 in 2023 to 521 attacks in 2024, marking a 70 percent increase

from the previous year.⁶⁶ Out of the total 521 attacks in 2024, 335 were carried out by the TTP and its local affiliated factions, marking a significant from 208 in 2023.⁶⁷ In 2024, at least 538 personnel from security forces and LEAs and 355 civilians lost their lives in these terrorist attacks.⁶⁸

In this context, the Taliban’s nascent rapprochement with India perturbs Pakistan. Pakistan is worried that India could leverage its improved ties with the Taliban to support the TTP to destabilize the country. In the past, Pakistan has accused India of collaborating with the former Western-backed Afghan government and its intelligence agencies to provide financial, logistical, and operational support to the TTP. As the Taliban continues to back/host the TTP, the BLA, and other anti-Pakistan terrorist groups, India could use its improved relationship with the Taliban to provide funding and operational assistance to these terrorist and separatist outfits to disrupt Pakistan's territorial integrity through insurgency and hybrid warfare. The TTP and BLA not only target Pakistan but also Chinese nationals and infrastructure projects in the country. This could also allow New Delhi to hurt Pakistan’s economy through

⁶³ Ghalib Nihad, “5 Killed, at least a dozen injured in blast at Quetta’s Serena hotel,” *Dawn*, April 22, 2021, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1619534>.

⁶⁴ Shahid Ali and Raj Verma, “The Taliban-TTP Nexus and Pakistan’s Rising Security Challenges,” *Middle East Policy*, November 21, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mepo.12787>.

⁶⁵ Baqir Sajjad Syed, “TTP Still Gets Financial, Logistic Support from Afghan Taliban,” *Dawn*, February 15, 2025, <https://www.dawn.com/news/1892006>.

⁶⁶ PIPS, “Pakistan Security Report 2024,” *Pakistan Institute for Peace Studies*, (2 January 2024), available at: https://www.pakpips.com/web/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Overview_PIPS-Security-Report-2024.pdf.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

systematic maneuvering and targeting. Frustrated over the Taliban's inaction against the TTP, Pakistan has undertaken a pressure campaign to persuade the Taliban into reviewing its growing engagement with India and severing its ties with the TTP. In November 2023, Pakistan announced that it will no longer "advocate the Taliban's case at the international level," and scale down its engagement with the Taliban government.⁶⁹ Pakistan has also placed severe restrictions on Afghan transit trade and imposed a ten percent duty on Afghan imports.⁷⁰ To put further pressure on the Taliban, Islamabad has also expelled more than 541,000 undocumented Afghan refugees from Pakistan.⁷¹

However, since establishing their rule in Afghanistan, the Taliban have asserted their independence from Pakistan, and that is being expressed through defiance and an unwillingness to act on Islamabad's demands, even at the risk of damaging their bilateral relationship with Pakistan. Over the past three years, the Taliban have adopted an increasingly

⁶⁹ Kamran Yousaf, 'Pakistan shifts stance on Afghan Taliban'. *The Express Tribune*, (2 November 2023). <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2445604/pakistan-shifts-stance-on-afghan-taliban>.

⁷⁰ Shahbaz Rana, "Govt tightens transit trade import regime," *The Express Tribune*, (4 October 2023), <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2439142/govt-tightens-transit-trade-import-regime>.

⁷¹ Al Jazeera, "Pakistan to Start Second Phase of Afghan Deportations," Al Jazeera, June 30, 2024, <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/6/30/pakistan-to-start-second-phase-of-afghan-deportations>.

nationalistic approach and independent foreign policy behavior and showcased a "strong desire to command respect at home and abroad" as underlined by globally "recognized notions of statehood and sovereignty," despite the unique nature of their relationship with Pakistan.⁷² Consequently, the Taliban have dismissed any possibility of foreign pressure/intervention regarding their relationship with other countries, including India. For instance, the Taliban's Acting Defense Minister, Mullah Yaqoob, while speaking on Pakistan's concerns over the Taliban's warming ties with India, remarked, "We are an independent country, and our foreign policy is guided by our national interests".⁷³

The Taliban's increasing willingness to pursue policies inimical to Pakistan's strategic interests has created a dilemma for Islamabad. On the one hand, Pakistan does not want to undermine its relationship and decades-long investment in the Taliban. On the other hand, the Taliban's increasingly independent foreign policy behavior, especially its harboring of the TTP and its newfound willingness to develop closer ties with India, poses a potent challenge to

⁷² Andrew Watkins, 'The Taliban One Year On'. *CTC Sentinel* 15, no. 8 (2022):1-15.

⁷³ The Express Tribune, "Taliban Willing to Send Afghan Troops to India for Training: Mullah Yaqoob," *The Express Tribune*, June 4, 2022, <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2360038/no-issues-in-sending-army-personnel-to-india-for-training-taliban>.

Pakistan's critical security and strategic interests in Afghanistan. When the Taliban needed Pakistan for shelter and support to withstand the US and NATO forces in Afghanistan, they acted as an acquiescent client/partner due to their reliance on Pakistan for sanctuary and support. But now that the Taliban have consolidated their hold on power in Afghanistan, they are asserting their independence from Pakistan and focusing on their regime's interest first. While Islamabad is exerting pressure on the Taliban to prevent them from embarking on policies and actions adverse to Pakistan's interests and preferences, it no longer wields a preponderant leverage over the Taliban to gain compliance. Although losing hard-earned influence is unacceptable to Pakistan, it cannot use coercion to compel the Taliban to undertake decisions that run counter to their regime's core interests because doing so could accelerate the Taliban's détente with India, a scenario Pakistan wants to avoid at all costs. Thus, despite the Taliban's increasingly nationalistic and independent foreign policy approach, Pakistan does not want a breakup with the Taliban and cede Afghan strategic space, worrying that India may fill the void and jeopardize Pakistan's core interests.

Conclusion

Pakistan has long sought to achieve strategic depth in Afghanistan by cultivating a friendly government in Kabul. When the Taliban

regained power in Afghanistan in August 2021, Pakistan believed that they would look after Pakistan's security and strategic interests. Pakistan anticipated that the Taliban government would curtail India's political, economic, and strategic influence in Afghanistan. However, after the formation of IEA 2.0 in August 2021, the Taliban have turned the tables on Pakistan. Despite knowing Pakistan's strategic and security concerns, the Taliban have cozied up to India in IEA 2.0 to the detriment of Pakistan.

The Taliban leadership has reestablished diplomatic links with India and held direct meetings with high-ranking Indian officials. The meeting between Foreign Secretary Vikram Misri and Acting Foreign Minister Mawlawi Amir Khan Muttaqi marks a critical shift in the Taliban's longstanding India policy, which has had strategic implications for the region, particularly for Pakistan. India's close relations with the Taliban may allow the former to gain strategic depth in Afghanistan, which would be a reversal of fortunes for Pakistan. Believing that a growing nexus between India and the Taliban could put Pakistan in a strategic predicament, Islamabad has applied considerable economic, political, and even military pressure on the Taliban to compel them to promote and protect Pakistan's security and strategic interests in Afghanistan.

In addition to cozying up to India, the Taliban have also provided tacit support to the TTP, have armed the TTP, released leaders and foot soldiers of the TTP, and have been unwilling to reign in the group despite repeated requests, complaints, and protests by Islamabad. Likewise, the Taliban have refused to accept the Durand Line as the international border between the two countries, a demand that the Taliban rejected during IEA 1.0 as well. They have strongly opposed Pakistan's efforts to fence the border and have opened fire on Pakistan's security forces to prevent the fencing of the border. The Taliban wants an open border so that it can enhance the TTP's position as a powerbroker in Pakistan's domestic polity. This would provide the Taliban with substantial leverage over Islamabad, which the former can utilize to improve its bargaining position with Islamabad.

For Pakistan, the Taliban have proven to be unreliable partners. However, Pakistan has very few good options. A further deterioration in the Afghanistan-Pakistan bilateral ties will only aggravate the threat to Pakistan's national security, sovereignty, and territorial integrity. An improvement in ties, which is unlikely in the current circumstances, also does not guarantee that the Taliban will stop its tacit support to the TTP, accept the Durand Line as the international border, and/or curtail bilateral ties with India. The collapse of the IEA 2.0 is also against Pakistan's interests because it will lead to instability in Afghanistan and will most likely strengthen the IS-KP. This will also exacerbate the perilous security situation in Pakistan and metastasize socio-economic and political instability in Pakistan and the entire region. The Taliban have all the cards, and Pakistan finds itself in a catch-22 position. Thus, it will be difficult for Pakistan to find a solution to the problem of its own making.